

Director General,
Wildlife Conservation Department,
P.O.Box 368,
ADDIS ABABA,
Ethiopia.

J.G. Stephenson,
P.O.Box 642,
MOROGORO,
Tanzania.

J/2 AB

25th. July, 1966.

Sir,

I have the honour to acknowledge receipt of your notification for the vacancy of Game Warden, forwarded to me by the Senior Game Warden under cover of his letter of the 11th. July, 1966.

I regret to inform you that I am not in a position to make firm application for the post as I am fully committed to the service of the Tanzania National Parks for an indefinite period. However, I should like my name to be borne in mind should you be advertising any other posts in Wildlife management which would be suitable for me as a married man. I would here mention that my experience with the Tanzania National Parks covers nearly four years, all of which time has been spent in founding new National Parks from scratch involving their administration, selecting and gazetting of boundaries, building, road-surveying and construction, vehicle maintenance and wildlife management. I am 46 years of age and am physically fit. I possess a current Private Pilot's Licence. I have no degree qualification. I was in the Administration of the Tanganyika Government from 1948 to 1962 inclusive.

I should like to make it quite clear that I would feel free to take up other appointment only as and when the Tanzania National Parks should Africanise my present post or on any other change occurring in the Tanzania National Parks which would substantially affect my present terms of service.

I have the honour to be, Sir,

Your obedient servant,

